

REFERENCES

1. WEBER W., "*Ueber Die Specifische Warme Fester Korper Insbesondere Der Metalle*", Pogg. Ann. der. Phys., 20, 1830, pp. 177-213.
2. THOMSON W. (Lord Kelvin), "*On the dynamical theory of heat*", Trans. Roy. Soc. Edingburgh, 20 (1853), pp. 261-288.
3. STANLEY P., CHAN W.K., "*SPATE stress studies of plates and rings under in-plane loading*", Experimental Mechanics, vol. 26, n° 4, 1986, pp. 360-370.
4. WÖLFEL M., FEICKERT W., "*comparison of thermoelastic stress analysis and finite elements results*", Proc. of 9th Int. conference on exp. Mechanics, Kopenhagen, vol. 2, 1990, pp. 748-758.
5. OWENS R.H., "*Applications of the termoelastic effect to typical aerospace composite materials*", Proc. SPIE conference, Stress Analysis by Thermoelastic Techniques, London, vol. 731, 1987, pp. 74-85.
6. SANDOR B.I., LOHR D.T., SCHMID K.C., "*Nondestructive testing using differential infrared thermography*", Materials Evaluation, vol. 45, 1987, pp. 392-395.
7. WONG, A. K., "*A Non-Adiabatic Thermoelastic Theory for Composite Laminates*", J. Phys. Chem. Solids, 52 , 1991 , pp. 483-494.
8. VAN HEMELRIJCK, D., SCHILLEMANS, L., et al. , "*Numerical Analysis of The Thermoelastic Effect in Laminated Structures and its use in the Identification of Defects*", SMP meeting AGARD '92, Patras, Greece, May '92
9. WHITAKER, S., "*Fundamental Principles of Heat Transfer*", Robert E. Krieger Publishing Company, Malabar, FA, 262, 1985.
10. CHAPMAN, A. J., *Heat Transfer*, MacMillan, New York, 1974.
11. DUNN, S. A., LOMBARDO, D., SPARROW, J.G., "*Stress and Vibration: Recent Developments in Industrial Measurement and Analysis*", Proc. SPIE conf., London, 1989.

ULTRASONIC INSPECTION OF LARGE COMPOSITE COMPONENTS IMPROVEMENTS FOR HIGH RESOLUTION AND REPRODUCIBILITY

W. Hillger, German Aerospace Research Establishment (DLR), P.O. Box 3267,
D-3300 Braunschweig, Germany
C. Valdecantos, TECAL, S.A., Jativa,7; 28007 Madrid, Spain

Keywords: Quality control, CFRP-component, ultrasonic testing, inspection system, high speed testing, software, pull-down menus, high dynamic range, peakdetector, C-scan

ABSTRACT

For the special requirements of the quality control of large composite components a high resolution ultrasonic inspection system was developed in a joint venture of two companies: TECAL in Spain and of Engineering office Dr. Hillger in Germany. The squirter inspection system consists of a four axis manipulation system with a length of 12 m and a scanning speed up to 750 mm/s, a computer controlled flaw detector HFUS 2000, a PC and a color printer. The dynamic range is 84 dB without any gain adjustment in a single C-scan. This system provides up to 4 channels which can be set with different frequency filters. The software (written by TECAL) with easy handling pull-down menus provides all settings of the manipulation and of the flaw detector on the keyboard of the computer. The data are stored on an optical disk.

1. INTRODUCTION

High performance materials such as carbon-fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) are attractive materials for aircraft and aerospace components. Their application to primary aircraft structures requires a high precision quality control.

Ultrasonic testing is a well established non destructive technique which has been extensively used in research and in industry [1].

This technique is able to detect typical defects such as delaminations, porosity, inclusions and inhomogenities [2-6]. CFRP laminates are inhomogeneous and anisotropic materials; therefore ultrasonic attenuation is relatively high. CFRP components are often curved, stringer stiffed and have different thicknesses in a range of 2 to 40 mm. The horizontal tail plane of the A340 for example has a length of 8.7 m, a width of 1.8 m and a thickness from 4 to 22 mm. The ultrasonic inspection technique had to be adapted and further developed for such components.

2. US-TESTING OF COMPOSITES

Fig. 1 shows the principle of US-testing. For the inhomogeneity of the material and the different velocities of resin and fibres, usually a normal angle of incidens of the sound is used. Through-transmission (left hand side in Fig. 1) and echo-technique (right hand side) are two basic inspection techniques. The echo-technique is useful for manual (in-service) inspection and for immersion technique. The ultrasonic pulse is reflected by a flaw or by the backwall of the component and received with the same transducer. In the case of a constant material-thickness, a gate range time

(time interval) for the amplitude measurement is used. A delamination causes nearly a 100 per cent sound reflection and gives an echo which is higher than the threshold (Fig. 1, left hand side). The through transmission technique is useful for the inspection of CFRP-parts with large and different thicknesses. Two transducers on both sides of the component are necessary; one transmitter and one receiver. The transducers are built in water jet; this squirter technique gives a reproducible coupling to the component. Defects produce a "shadow area", therefore the amplitude will decrease. If the thickness of the component is constant, a "flaw threshold" can be used. The effect of sound damping of defects can be increased using double-through-transmission technique for thin laminates (Fig. 1).

The sound pressure amplitude p decreases exponentially along its path d :

$$p_d = p_0 e^{-\alpha d} \quad (1),$$

where α is the sound attenuation and p_0 the sound pressure at the interface of the component. Therefore the linear amplitude measurement is found to be unsatisfactory. The dynamic range of the sound pressure amplitude of a complex composite component can easily reach more than 1:10,000 (80 dB) during scanning. For this application, a special peak detector has to be developed (see chapter 3.2). The large size of the components require a special manipulation system (up to 12 m length) and a very fast scanning speed in order to have a short inspection time.

3. DEVELOPED US-INSPECTION SYSTEM "SARA"

3.1 MECHANICS

The mechanics of SARA System can be designed to fit almost any particular requirement regarding part, size or shape. Fig 2 shows a typical structure with dimensions of: 12000 mm for the X-axis, 2000 mm for Y_1 -, Y_2 -axes and 3000 mm for the Z-axis. The mechanics provides high resolution: 500 steps per revolution and 1000 steps in half step mode. Stepper motors are used for all axes, with planetary reductions of 1:5 or 1:10 depending on the particular requirement of speed and torque.

Toothed belt driving is used for X and Z axes and precision ball spindle for Y_1 , Y_2 axes. This makes the system able to perform accurate interpolation so that complex curved surfaces can be followed. The maximum scanning speed in X axis is over 700 mm per second. Inclined scan in any direction can also be performed, keeping the speed well over 500 mm per second. Programming a scan is an easy task for the operator. A wireless operated interactive remote control is available to make the axes positioning friendly and accurate.

3.2 SQUIRTER TRANSDUCER

Ultrasonic energy coupling to the part is achieved by a suitable water jet technique. Fig. 3 gives an impression of squirter testing. A careful design of the nozzles makes possible to keep acceptable signal-to noise ratio even at very long nozzle-to part distance. As an example, 200 mm distance is still possible for inspection.

3.3 ULTRASONIC ELECTRONICS

3.3.1 Overview

Fig. 4 shows the block diagram of the two channel version of the HFUS 2000/84 which was developed for the special requirements of composites. The inspection system consists of several modules which are built in a 19" -case. All modules are connected to a common bus which is combined to a computer via an opto-isolated interface. The system provides testing with up to 4 channels. Each channel has a separate pulser/preamplifier with four receiver filters (1.0; 2.2, 5.0 and a broadband channel 0.5 to 12 MHz). The pulser/preamplifier is mounted near the receiver transducers, so that the cable length can be relatively short in order to prevent noise. The amplifiers are designed for low noise and high dynamic range. The high dynamic range of 84 dB in a single C-scan requires a special peakdetector, which had to be developed for this special application.

3.3.2 Digital logarithmic peakdetector

The passive peak measurement method used in a proportional monitor of a standard ultrasonic flow detector is not useful for high-tech materials. The dynamic range in many cases is only 20 dB. The problem of the peak detection consists of fast detection of the highest amplitude within a given gate range with a high dynamic and storage of the value to the next measurement.

The new developed logarithmic peakdetector is based on a modified flash converter which directly digitizes the peak amplitude. This device consists of a serie of fast comparators connected with storages. The advantage of this digital method over analog ones is the high dynamic range (84 dB) and a fast response time (less than 2 ns!), no linearity errors and no changes in the memory after data acquisition. This digital peakdetector requires no calculation of the peak value and has a constant resolution (1 dB) over the whole dynamic range.

3.4 SOFTWARE

A very important factor is the software which provides not only the manipulation and settings of the ultrasonic flaw detector but also the storage of data and imaging of test results in C- scans. The pull down menus provide a very easy handling with many help functions.

4. TYPICAL RESULTS

Fig. 5 shows a C-scan of CFRP-step-wedge test specimen in double-through-transmission technique with thicknesses of 2.5, 5.5, 7.5 and 9.5 mm. The displayed dynamic range is 32 dB in 16 grey levels. Along the marked line the amplitude is plotted (Fig. 6). It is clearly displayed that each change of 3 mm in the thickness causes an amplitude change of 6 dB. The amplitude resolution of each thickness (damping) is constant so that defects can be clearly displayed as additional dampings.

Fig. 7 shows a C-scan of the CN-235 rudder. The tests were curried out with 2 MHz. The C-scan shows very clearly boam lines inside the part.

5. SUMMARY

High tech materials such as components of carbon fibre are very attractive for aircraft and airoespace components. The quality control gets more and more importance. Ultrasonic inspection is the most used non-destructive testing method. For the special requirements of the quality control of large composite components a high resolution ultrasonic inspection system was developed. The system is based on squirter through-transmission technique.

The mechanics consists of a four axis manipulation system with a length up to 12 m and a scanning speed up to 750 mm/s. The computer controlled ultrasonic flaw detector provides inspections up to four channels with separate pulser/preamplifiers. Each channel can be used with different filter frequencies. A special logarithmic digital peakdetector was developed which gives a dynamic range of 84 dB without any gain adjustment in a single C-scan.

The software (written by TECAL) with easy handling pull-down menus provides all settings of the manipulation and of the flaw detector on the keyboard of the computer. The data are stored on an optical disk. Typical results of composite components are shown.

6. REFERENCES

1. Scott, J. and G.Scala, C.M.: *A Review of Non-Destructive Testing of Composite Materials*. NDT International, April 1982, pp. 75-86.
2. Hagenmaier, D.J. and R. H. Fassbender, *Ultrasonic inspection of carbon-Epoxy composites*, Materials Evaluation, 43, April 1985, pp. 556-560
3. Bar-Cohen, Y.: *NDE of Fiber-Reinforced Composite Materials-A Review*, Materials Evalua-

tion,44, March 1986, pp. 446-454.

4. Hillger, W.: *Non-Destructive Analyses of Damage States in Laminated Composites by Ultrasonic Testing*. Conf. Proc. Ultrasonics International 1985, S.613-618, London, 2.-4. July 1985.

5. Hillger, W.: *US-Inspections of CFRP-Laminates with high resolution*. *Non-Destructive Testing*, Proc. of the 12th Conf. on NDT, Amsterdam, April 23-28, 1989, Vol. 2, S. 1561-1566

6. Hillger, W. : *Ultrasonic Imaging of damages in CFRP-Laminates*, 19th Internat. Symposium on Acoustical Imaging, 3.-5. 4. 91, Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Acoustical Imaging, Vol. 19, pp. 575-579, Plenum Press, New York and London 1992.

7. Hillger, W.: *A high frequency Peak Detector for US-test-pulses*. Ultrasonic International, London, 6-9 Juli 1987, Conf. Proc. S. 102-107

Fig. 1: US-Testing of CFRP

Fig. 2: SARA-Mechanics

Fig. 3: Ultrasonic squirter testing

Fig. 4: HFUS 2000-Blockdiagram

Fig. 5: C-Scan of CFRP-Specimen with different thickness

Fig. 6: Echodynamic (of one line in Fig. 5)

Fig. 7: C-scan of the CN-235 rudder.